

Study Of Logistics Management and Cost Benefit Analysis For Green Field Highways

Mudimadugula Pavankumar¹, Makendran C² and Alok Kumar³

^{1,2,3}National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, India

Abstract This research investigates the factors influencing logistics management in highway construction and aims to rank them accordingly. The study employs the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for Factor Analysis, facilitating the identification and prioritization of these factors. Additionally, a mathematical Linear Programming (LP) model is developed to address transportation issues within the context of the construction project. The LP model is subsequently solved using Conventional Operational Research methods, specifically the Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM), the Modified Distribution Method (MODI), and LP SOLVER. By integrating both qualitative and quantitative approaches, this research contributes to a comprehensive understanding of logistics challenges in highway construction and provides practical solutions through mathematical modeling and operational research techniques. The findings aim to enhance decision-making processes and optimize logistics management strategies in the construction industry.

Keywords Logistics management, cost benefit analysis, Linear Programming, modified distribution method, green field highway

Introduction

Logistics management is the process of planning, implementing, and controlling the efficient and effective flow and storage of goods, services, and related information from point of origin to point of consumption in order to meet the needs of customers. Logistics management is critical in highway building because it ensures that the proper materials, equipment, and workers are available at the correct time and place to support seamless construction operations. In recent decades, there has been substantial focus within the field of supply chain and logistics management literature on the optimization of logistics operations (Steinrucke and Jahr, 2012). Broadly defined, logistics network optimization involves the efficient movement of diverse products from numerous sources to various end customers through a range of intermediate facilities (Ma and Suo, 2006). Mathematical linear programming (LP) models have emerged as powerful tools for solving transportation problems in highway projects. LP models provide a structured framework for representing and optimizing transportation costs, taking into account factors such as transportation distances, transportation modes, and transportation capacities. Excel LP Solver is a powerful tool that can be used to solve linear programming problems. Linear programming is a mathematical technique used to optimize a linear objective function, subject to linear equality and inequality constraints. The Excel LP Solver can be used to solve a wide range of optimization problems, including resource allocation, production planning, and transportation problems. It is especially useful for solving large-scale problems that would be difficult to solve manually. The Excel LP Solver is easy to use and can be accessed through the Solver add-in in Excel. It allows users to define the objective function and constraints of the problem, and then automatically finds the optimal solution. This can save a lot of time and effort compared to manual methods of solving linear programming problems. Conventional operational research methods, such as the transportation simplex method and the Vogel's approximation method, have traditionally been used to solve transportation problems. These methods are straightforward and relatively easy to implement, making them suitable for small-scale problems. However, they may encounter computational challenges when dealing with large-scale transportation problems with a significant number of variables and constraints.

Literature Review

S Choudhari and A Tindwani (2017) discusses the importance of logistics optimization in road construction projects. The authors argue that logistics costs can account for up to 25% of the total project cost, and that optimization can lead to significant savings. They propose a linear programming (LP) model to optimize the material logistics of a road construction project. The model takes into account the following factors: quantity and type of materials required, location of the borrow pits and construction sites, transportation costs, constraints on the availability of materials and equipment. Ratapol Wudhikarn et al. (2018) conducted a thorough literature review to delve into the significance of intellectual capital in the realm of logistics management. The authors meticulously identify the crucial elements integral to a successful logistics management plan. Swanson et al. (2017) investigate how theories from different disciplines may be applied to logistics and supply chain management. According to the authors, logistics management necessitates an awareness of the shifting methods in which ideas are applied. This systematic literature review (SLR) incorporates previously unseen timeframes, including the most recent period from 2010 to 2015, to fill this research gap and help scholars understand this abundance of new material. Ghoumrassi et al. (2017) contend that the satisfaction of customers is influenced by the efficacy of warehouse and inventory management solutions, the seamless integration and control of the supply chain within the company's operational framework, the effective sharing and management of Information Communication Technology (ICT) processes, the coordinated handling of common key performance indicators (KPIs) and performance

data, the proficiency in logistics-related knowledge and skills from the supplier, and the implementation of environmentally friendly logistics solutions by the supplier. Feng et al. (2021) explored more about operations management research pertaining to smart logistics. The authors posit that this revolution has captivated the interest of scholars in engineering, logistics, transportation, and management fields. The focus of operations management research on smart logistics primarily revolves around the utilization of foundational technologies, business logic, operational frameworks, associated management systems, and the resolution of optimization challenges within specific scenarios. Gacuru et al. (2015) investigate the determinants influencing the efficiency of logistics performance among trading and manufacturing firms in Kenya. The authors conducted a quantitative study employing questionnaires distributed to various firms in the country. The gathered data underwent analysis through descriptive and inferential statistics. The research identified key factors affecting efficiency in logistics performance, namely transportation costs, inventory costs, warehousing costs, and order processing costs. The summary of literature review is efficient logistics management is crucial in road construction projects, where costs can escalate to 25% of the total project cost. A proposed Linear Programming (LP) model addresses material quantity, type, borrow pit location, and transportation costs, offering significant savings. Intellectual capital emerges as a key factor in logistics success, identified through a literature review. Exploration into logistics and supply chain management underscores the need for awareness of evolving methods, with a systematic literature review from 2010 to 2015 filling research gaps. Customer satisfaction hinges on effective warehouse and inventory management, seamless supply chain integration, ICT processes, shared KPIs, logistics expertise, and environmentally friendly solutions. Operations management research in smart logistics focuses on foundational technologies, business logic, frameworks, management systems, and optimization challenges. Determinants influencing logistics performance in Kenyan firms, identified through quantitative study, encompass transportation, inventory, warehousing, and order processing costs.

Objectives of the Study

1. To identify and rank the factors which affects logistics management during highway construction
2. To perform factor analysis by using SPSS software.
3. To develop mathematical linear programming model for transportation problems.
4. To Solve the LP model by using Conventional Operational Research methods (VAM&MODI) and LP solver.

Methodology

To gain a deeper understanding, let us examine a case study pertaining to highway building and identify the variables that impact the logistics management process. The prevalent international method of administering a questionnaire survey was employed to gather the viewpoints of participants on the variables impacting the logistics management while building a roadway. Academics, researchers, students, civil engineers, project managers, and planning in-charges were all given the survey questionnaire. In addition to providing a rating (weightage) based on their experience, participants were asked to list any additional aspects that affect logistics management. The questionnaire consists of 20 elements, and responses were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, where 5 was assigned for very important, 4 for important, 3 for somewhat important, and 2 for slightly important, 1 very least important.

Methodology

Identification and ranking of factors

Factors affecting Logistics Management:

The following 20 factors affecting logistics management were found from a review of the literature.

1. Location of camp, offices and plants
2. Storage and warehousing
3. To plan for timely material supply
4. Efficient allocation and maintenance of equipment
5. Effective Transportation of materials
6. Proper vehicle routing and traffic management
7. Maintain optimal stock levels.
8. Utilization of Technology and resource optimization tools
9. Monitoring and controlling logistics costs.
10. Project Scheduling: Create a detailed construction schedule.
11. Lead Time: Lead time from source to destination
12. Project duration
13. Labor Management: Recruiting and training
14. Design Changes: Adapt logistics to accommodate design modifications.
15. Communication: Establishing effective stakeholder communication
16. Quality Control: Ensure material adherence to specifications.
17. Environmental Clearances and Regulations

- 18. Disruptions due to weather
- 19. Safety: Prioritize safety for all personnel and road users.
- 20. Risk Management: Preparedness for unforeseen events.

Methodology flowchart

Fig 1: Methodology flowchart

A total of 160 questionnaire surveys were sent by email and in person to civil engineers, project managers, professors, researchers, and students. The survey received 104 responses from a total of 160 participants. The response rate was 65%, which was satisfactory because a response rate of more than 40% is considered acceptable.

Frequency index: Frequency of response was assessed by using the following frequency index

$$FI = \frac{\sum A(n)}{5N}$$

Where:

A = constant expressing the weight assigned to each response (Ranging 1 for very least important and 5 for very important)
 n = frequency of each response and
 N = Total number of responses.

SPSS: SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) is a widely used software for statistical analysis in social science research. It offers a user-friendly interface for data manipulation, descriptive statistics, and advanced statistical modeling

Data Analysis: The data analysis is performed for two purposes ranking and factor analysis

In this data, the ranking of factors is crucial for understanding the relative importance of different elements. A higher rank indicates greater perceived significance, while a lower rank suggests lower importance. Analyzing the order of factors allows to focus on addressing or emphasizing the most influential aspects, aiding in targeted decision-making. Additionally, it provides valuable insights for prioritizing interventions or improvements based on the perceived impact of each factor. Monitoring and controlling logistics costs, to plan for timely material supply, Project Scheduling, Effective Transportation of materials are the crucial factors which needs to be focused.

Table 1: Frequency Index for the factors affecting logistics management

Factors Affecting Logistics Management	FI	Rank
Monitoring and controlling logistics costs.	0.838462	1
Quality Control: Ensure material adherence to specifications.	0.834615	2
To plan for timely material supply	0.823077	3
Effective Transportation of materials	0.819231	4
Project Scheduling: Create a detailed construction schedule.	0.819231	4
Efficient allocation and maintenance of equipment	0.815385	5
Location of camp, offices and plants	0.807692	6
Safety: Prioritize safety for all personnel and road users.	0.796154	7
Communication: Establishing effective stakeholder communication	0.788462	8
Proper vehicle routing and traffic management	0.784615	9
Storage and warehousing	0.784615	10
Utilization of Technology and resource optimization tools	0.780769	11
Project duration	0.780769	11
Risk Management: Preparedness for unforeseen events.	0.780769	12
Lead Time: Lead time from source to destination	0.773077	13
Maintain optimal stock levels.	0.769231	14
Environmental Clearances and Regulations	0.769231	14
Labor Management: Recruiting and training	0.765385	15
Design Changes: Adapt logistics to accommodate design modifications.	0.757692	16
Disruptions due to weather	0.742308	17

Reliability analysis

Reliability analysis helps determine the degree of consistency or stability in the measurements taken by a set of items or questions. For example, questionnaire designed to measure a specific construct, reliability analysis assesses whether the items in the questionnaire consistently measure the same underlying concept. Researchers often create scales or instruments composed of multiple items to measure a particular construct. Reliability analysis helps evaluate the effectiveness of these scales. A reliable scale should yield consistent results over time and across different samples. After performing reliability analysis, the Cronbach’s alpha value is 0.963. Hence this data is more reliable to do factor analysis.

Factor Analysis

Factor analysis in SPSS is a statistical method used to identify underlying factors or dimensions within a set of observed variables. It helps simplify data by grouping correlated variables into common factors, aiding in the interpretation of complex relationships. SPSS provides tools for extracting factors, assessing their significance, and interpreting their impact on the observed variables. Researchers use factor analysis to uncover latent structures and reduce data complexity for more meaningful insights. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure assesses the adequacy of a dataset for factor analysis, with values closer to 1 indicating better suitability. Typically, a KMO value above 0.6 is considered acceptable. On the other hand, Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity evaluates whether correlations between variables are significant for factor analysis. A small p-value (usually below 0.05) in Bartlett’s test suggests substantial correlations, supporting the meaningful application of factor analysis. Both KMO and Bartlett’s test serve as crucial diagnostics to ensure the reliability and validity of factor analysis results, helping researchers make informed decisions about the appropriateness of the data for this statistical technique.

Table 2: SPSS output for KMO and Bartlett’s test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.873
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2012.503
	df	190
	Sig.	0.000

Table 3: SPSS output for Total Variance

Total Variance									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.831	59.154	59.154	11.831	59.154	59.154	4.943	24.713	24.713
2	1.222	6.110	65.264	1.222	6.110	65.264	4.207	21.033	45.746
3	1.077	5.383	70.648	1.077	5.383	70.648	3.756	18.778	64.524
4	1.043	5.217	75.865	1.043	5.217	75.865	2.268	11.341	75.865

The prominent factors revealed in this study demonstrate a favorable quality, each encompassing at least three variables per factor, as suggested by Yong and Pearce (2013). Loading values below 0.550 were excluded from the analysis for precision. The factors were subsequently named by taking into account the underlying causes associated with each factor. This approach ensures a robust identification of meaningful and relevant factors in the study. Monitoring and controlling logistics costs, to plan for timely material supply, Project Scheduling, Effective Transportation of materials are the crucial factors which needs to be focused.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

<p>Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.</p> <p>1.Group I : Logistics planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location of camp, offices and plant • To plan for timely material supply • Effective Transportation of materials • Monitoring and controlling logistics costs. • Storage and warehousing <p>2.Group II: Resource Optimization and Scheduling</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain optimal stock levels. • Utilization of Technology and resource optimization tools • Proper vehicle routing and traffic management. • Lead Time: Lead time from source to destination • Project Scheduling: Create a detailed construction schedule
--

- 3.Group III:Project Management and Quality Assurance**
- Labor Management: Recruiting and training
 - Design Changes: Adapt logistics to accommodate design modifications.
 - Project duration
 - Quality Control: Ensure material adherence to specifications.
 - Safety: Prioritize safety for all personnel and road users.
- 4.Group IV: Stakeholder Communication and Risk Management**
- Communication: Establishing effective stakeholder communication
 - Disruptions due to weather
 - Risk Management: Preparedness for unforeseen events.
 - Environmental considerations

Table 4: SPSS output of Rotated Component matrix (Rotation converged in 14 iteration)

	Rotated Component Matrix			
	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Location of camp, offices and plants	0.830	0.121	0.209	0.131
Storage and warehousing	0.698	0.443	0.226	0.128
To plan for timely material supply	0.734	0.486	0.221	0.075
Efficient allocation and maintenance of equipment	0.493	0.582	0.475	-0.031
Effective Transportation of materials	0.685	0.534	0.298	-0.065
Proper vehicle routing and traffic management	0.369	0.667	0.293	0.14
Maintain optimal stock levels.	0.472	0.637	0.103	0.363
Utilization of Technology and resource optimization tools	0.338	0.598	0.233	0.398
Monitoring and controlling logistics costs.	0.716	0.363	0.243	0.32
Project Scheduling: Create a detailed construction schedule.	0.156	0.714	0.469	0.095
Lead Time: Lead time from source to destination	0.225	0.765	0.175	0.322
Project duration	0.208	0.195	0.808	0.15
Labor Management: Recruiting and training	0.232	0.348	0.749	0.043
Design Changes: Adapt logistics to accommodate design modifications.	0.198	0.485	0.62	0.213
Communication: Establishing effective stakeholder communication	0.528	0.321	0.394	0.368
Quality Control: Ensure material adherence to specifications.	0.55	0.245	0.556	0.402
Environmental Clearances and Regulations	0.444	0.25	0.37	0.431
Disruptions due to weather	0.068	0.218	0.124	0.882
Safety: Prioritize safety for all personnel and road users.	0.504	0.087	0.585	0.482
Risk Management: Preparedness for unforeseen events.	0.532	0.159	0.530	0.368

LP Model Development

Developing mathematical Linear Programming model for transportation problem:

From the rankings it is evident that transportation is one the critical factor for efficient logistics management. We take the highway construction case study to formulate the mathematical linear programming model for transportation problem and solve with different methods to get cost effective model. Considering to transport concrete from two origins to different destinations required. Let’s find out the best suitable method for the explained scenario.

Transportation Problem:

A type of linear programming problem specifically designed to determine the most cost-effective or profit-maximizing way to distribute goods from multiple sources (supply points) to multiple destinations (demand points).

It involves variables like:

- Supply at each source

- Demand at each destination
- Cost or profit associated with transporting goods between each source-destination pair

The objective is usually to minimize total transportation cost or maximize total profit.

Table 5: Transportation Problem Matrix

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Supply
Batching Plant 1	24	25	20	18	18	17	592
Batching Plant 2	17	18	19	21	27	22	592
Demand	23	93	290	115	185	556	

Mathematical Linear Programming Model for the Transportation Problem:

Decision Variables:

X_{ij} : Quantity of product transported from Batching Plant i to Destination j ($i=1,2; j=1,2,\dots,6$)

Objective Function:

$$\text{minimize } Z = 24x_{11} + 25x_{12} + 20x_{13} + 18x_{14} + 18x_{15} + 17x_{16} + 17x_{21} + 18x_{22} + 19x_{23} + 21x_{24} + 27x_{25} + 22x_{26}$$

Constraints:

Supply Constraints:

Total quantity of product shipped from each Batching Plant cannot exceed its available supply

$$x_{11} + x_{12} + x_{13} + x_{14} + x_{15} + x_{16} \leq 592 \text{ (for Batching Plant 1)}$$

$$x_{21} + x_{22} + x_{23} + x_{24} + x_{25} + x_{26} \leq 592 \text{ (for Batching Plant 2)}$$

Demand Constraints:

Total quantity of product received at each Destination must meet its demand.

$$x_{11} + x_{21} \geq 23 \text{ (for Destination 1)}$$

$$x_{12} + x_{22} \geq 93 \text{ (for Destination 2)}$$

$$x_{13} + x_{23} \geq 290 \text{ (for Destination 3)}$$

$$x_{14} + x_{24} \geq 115 \text{ (for Destination 4)}$$

$$x_{15} + x_{25} \geq 185 \text{ (for Destination 5)}$$

$$x_{16} + x_{26} \geq 556 \text{ (for Destination 6)}$$

Non-negativity Constraints:

Quantity of product transported cannot be negative

$$x_{ij} \geq 0 \text{ for all } i \text{ and } j.$$

Analysis and Interpretation:

Vogels Approximation method:

Table 6: Transportation Problem solution by using VAM after 8 iterations

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Supply
Batching Plant 1	24	25	20	18	18	17	592
Batching Plant 2	17	18	19	21	27	22	592
Batching Plant 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	83
Demand	23	93	290	115	185	556	

Total Minimum Cost:

$$= (83 \times 0 + 185 \times 18 + 28 \times 17 + 93 \times 18 + 407 \times 17 + 149 \times 22 + 115 \times 21 + 207 \times 19)$$

$$= 22025$$

Modified Distribution Method (MODI):

Table 7: Transportation Problem solution by using MODI after 9 iterations

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	Supply	Total
Batching Plant 1	24	25	20	18	18	17	592	
Batching Plant 2	17	18	19	21	27	22	592	
Batching Plant 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	83	
Demand	23	93	290	115	185	556		

Minimum Cost

$$= (18 \times 102 + 17 \times 490 + 17 \times 28 + 18 \times 93 + 19 \times 290 + 21 \times 115 + 22 \times 66 + 0 \times 83)$$

$$= 21693$$

LP Solver

LP Solver is a powerful software tool utilized for solving transportation problems within the realm of linear programming. Specifically designed to optimize objective functions, it efficiently minimizes transportation costs by allocating goods from multiple suppliers to various destinations. LP Solver employs algorithmic approaches, such as the Simplex or Interior-Point methods, to iteratively navigate through feasible solutions and converge upon the optimal solution. With a user-friendly interface, it allows for the input of data, definition of decision variables, and setting of constraints. Its applications span across diverse industries, providing valuable support in logistics and supply chain optimization, enabling informed decisions for cost-effective resource allocation.

Total Minimum cost from LP solver = 22085

Table 8: Comparison between VAM, MODI and LP solver

Characteristic	Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM)	MODI Method	LP Solver
Optimality	May not always guarantee optimal solution	Provides iterative improvement	Designed to find the optimal solution
Complexity	Relatively simple and easy to implement	Involves iteration steps	Requires formulation of LP model and software
Accuracy	Reasonable solutions but may require iterations	Provides precise solutions	Offers precise and accurate solutions
Applicability	Suitable for small to moderately sized problems	Suitable for moderate-sized problems	Suitable for problems of various sizes and complexities
Method Type	Heuristic	Iterative Improvement	Linear Programming
Initialization	Provides an initial feasible solution	Utilizes initial solution from methods like VAM	Requires initial formulation of LP model
Loop Handling	Does not explicitly handle loops	Identifies and resolves loops	N/A (Handles through LP optimization)
Scalability	Suitable for small to moderate-sized problems	Suitable for moderate-sized problems	Suitable for problems of various sizes

Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to identify the factors affecting logistics management during highway construction. SPSS is essential for analyzing Likert scale data as it efficiently handles the statistical calculations required to interpret responses. In SPSS performed Frequency analysis, Reliability analysis, Factor analysis, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. The 20 factors which were identified were ranked, grouped, and analyzed. The four top most factors identified as Monitoring and controlling logistics costs, to plan for timely material supply, Project Scheduling and effective Transportation of materials. These factors should be focused more to minimize the cost. The

grouping of 20 affects using factor analysis resulted into 4 factors as Logistics Planning, Resource Optimization & Scheduling, Project Management & Quality Assurance and Risk Mitigation & Communication. The Factor Rating Method helps in optimizing resource allocation, minimizing risks, and aligning facility choices with organizational goals and strategic decision-making. This method enhances transparency, facilitating a comprehensive and efficient evaluation of potential locations for effective facility planning. After solving using the VAM, MODI, and LP solver, it appears that the LP solver provides about realistic results, allowing us to satisfy the entire demand. The LP solver offers great flexibility and eliminates the need for iterations, unlike the VAM and Modi method.

References

1. Wudhikarn, R., Chakpitak, N., & Neubert, G. (2018), "A literature review on performance measures of logistics management: an intellectual capital perspective", *International Journal of Production Research*, 56:4490-4520.
2. Swanson, D., Goel, L., Francisco, K., & Stock, J. (2017), "Applying Theories from Other Disciplines to Logistics and Supply Chain Management: A Systematic Literature Review", *Transportation Journal*, 56:299–356.
3. K. Malleswara Rao, "A Literature Review on Operations Management of Logistics and Supply Chain: Issues and Directions", *International Journal of Recent Engineering Research and Development (IJRERD)*, 1:9.
4. Ghoumrassi, A., & Tigu, G. (2017), "The impact of the logistics management in customer satisfaction", *In Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, 11:292-301.
5. Feng, B., Ye, Q. (2021), "Operations management of smart logistics: A literature review and future research", *Front. Eng. Manag*, 8:344–355
6. Gacuru, W. & Kabare, K. (2015), "Factors affecting efficiency in logistics performance of trading a distribution firms based in Jomo Kenyatta International Airport area", *International Academic Journal of Procurement and Supply Chain Management*, 1 :50-71
7. Williams, B., Brown, T. and Onsmann, A. (2010), "Exploratory factor analysis: A five-step guide for novices", *Australian Journal of Paramedicine*, 8: 1–13
8. Akoa, B.B. (2011), "Cost overruns and time delays in highway and bridge projects in developing countries - experiences from Cameroon", MS diss., Michigan State University.
9. Choudhari, S. and Tindwani, A. (2017), "Logistics optimisation in road construction project", *Construction Innovation*, 17 :158-179.
10. Chandrasekaran Balaji Venkateswaran and Rajiah Murugasan. (2017), "Time delay and cost overrun of road over bridge (ROB) construction projects in India", *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 22: 79–96.
11. Chotechoei and Nisarath (2018), "Factors Affecting the Efficiency of Logistics Management of Small and Medium Enterprises in Thailand: A Case Study of Logistics Service Providers (July 1, 2018)," *PSAKU International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 7.
12. Daugherty, P.J. (2011), "Review of logistics and supply chain relationship literature and suggested research agenda", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 41:16-31.
13. Steinrücke, M. and Jahr, M. (2012), "Tactical planning in supply chain networks with customer oriented single sourcing", *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, Vol. 23 :259-279.
14. Ma, H. and Suo, C. (2006), "A model for designing multiple products logistics networks", *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 36 :127-135.